

Squamous cell carcinoma associated granular cell tumour with progressive FDG accumulation

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ABSTRACT Granular cell tumor is a usually benign rare tumor of middle age women with variable FDG uptake patterns. The case that we presented was the first in the literature as far as we know with presentation of two different concurrent pathologies and progressive FDG uptake. Since the case was considered unresectable the patients received further chemotherapy. The patients' PET/CT results showed progression under treatment.

KEYWORDS squamous, granular cell tumor, fdg, pet

Introduction

Granular cell tumor (GCT) is a rare tumor that was firstly described by Abrikossoff in 1926 as a myeloblastoma, [1] however today it is documented to be an estrogen dependent peripheral nerve Schwann's cell tumor [2]. These tumors rarely might be malignant [3]. The FDG accumulation of these tumors is variable with reported low and high uptake in previous case reports with limited number of previous reports [2, 4]. Additionally metastatic patient with GCT with low FDG uptake in PET/CT has been reported previously [5]. These tumors might be located at any site of the body but usually at the tongue, skin, breast and gastrointestinal tract [4]. The tumors are usually asymptomatic but may be problematic in certain sites as a conflicting factor with malign tumor like in breast [1].

The aim of this presentation is to demonstrate an interesting and rare case report with granular cell tumor and squamous cell carcinoma at the same site with follow up F-18 FDG PET/CT follow up results.

Case Report

The case that we present is 68 years old female patient with previous diagnosis of various malignant tumors including na-

zopharyngeal carcinoma, in situ colon carcinoma and left middle ear squamous cell carcinoma which were operated and two years after the operation recurrent tumor at the middle ear occurred. During the second operation the temporal muscle flap was inserted at the operation site. The patient was referred for PET/CT imaging; performed at >4 hour fasting condition and injection of approximately 370 MBq; F-18 FDG PET/CT imaging after one hour waiting period by a PET/CT scanner (GE, Discovery PET/CT 610, US); one year after the last operation which showed slightly increased activity at the operation site three months after the last radiotherapy (Figure 1). Four months after the first imaging the second PET/CT examination was performed and demonstrated progressive FDG accumulation at the same site (Figure 2). In order to lack of the response the chemotherapy protocol changed and patients' tumor was regressive in the PET/CT control (Figure 3).

Figure 1. Fusion and PET images of the patient with progressive FDG accumulation in transaxial slices in the left middle ear region corresponding previously excised primary tumour identified as a local recurrence.

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Figure 2. The transaxial, sagittal and coronal projection F-18 FDG PET/CT images of the same hypermetabolic lesion adjacent to the bone 27x30 mm in size (a, b, c) (SUVmax=22.3). A biopsy was performed for diagnosis from the four quadrants of the lesion. The pathology results revealed benign granular cell tumour in three of four specimens. However, there was also squamous cell carcinoma at one of the samples (d).

Figure 3. Transaxial projection images of the patient showing metabolic regression of the lesion in the follow up after chemotherapy.

Discussion

The different pathology at the same specimen is a rare phenomenon in the literature which was not reported previously with PET/CT results. This case report represents the first case with different tumors in the same and with FDG PET/CT results and follow up. The significant increase in the middle ear of the patient might be because of the squamous cell tumor component of the combined lesion due to the fact that the FDG accumulation faded after different chemotherapy protocol. In this case we cannot clearly indicate that the FDG uptake is a result of GCT. Previously the lung malign GCT was presented by Cheng et al. with high FDG uptake [6]. Hamada et al. also reported slightly increased FDG accumulation in a soft tissue benign GCT [7]. A hypermetabolic sellar tumor with GCT pathology was also reported in a previous series with histopathological results [8]. However there is limited number of case reports about the FDG uptake characteristics of GCT. However this case report is a rare cases report with known multiple cancers additionally the pathology showing two different pathologies at the same site. FDG PET/CT and MRI images of a patient with the diagnosis of malignant granular cell tumor of the pericardium have been presented previously [9]. These tumors might be malignant in approximately 1-3

Competing Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in this study.

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